

PERFORMANCE IN CPA LICENSURE EXAMINATION OF DWCSJ GRADUATES: A PROPOSED INTERVENTION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 1

Pages: 19-31

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1838

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11217400

Manuscript Accepted: 04-24-2024

Performance in CPA Licensure Examination of DWCSJ Graduates: A Proposed Intervention

Mark Jing D. Tayactac*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research study defines the performance in CPA Licensure Examination of DWCSJ graduates. Mainly, the nature of this study is a descriptive research using descriptive-correlational design to assess the variables of this study which included the profiles of the respondents in terms of grades in major subjects, IQ level, EQ status, and socioeconomic status; and their attitude towards CPA review as well as the relationship of these variables to their performance in CPA Licensure Examination. The questionnaire is the main research instrument used for the gathering of data. It composed of three parts: Socioeconomic status, EQ Status, and Attitude towards CPA Review. The researcher asked permission from the Office of the Registrar to obtain a copy of grades to be used in this research study and; to test the relationship of IQ level with their performance in licensure examination, the researcher seeks the consent of the Guidance Counselor for the results of respondent's IQ level. The regression analysis for multiple independent variables was used to find the degree of relationship between the variables under study. Multiple-regression stepwise technique was used to establish the relationship between the independent variables: grades in major subjects, IQ level, EQ status, attitude towards CPA review and socioeconomic status; and the dependent variable, performance in CPA Licensure Examination. The results showed that respondent's profiles in terms of grades in major subjects, EQ status and socioeconomic status; and attitude towards CPA review were best indicators of good performance in CPA Licensure Examination. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profiles except IQ level and performance in CPA Licensure Examination, is therefore, rejected. Further, statistical research result ascertains the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the examinees' attitude towards CPA review and their level of CPA performance. It is essential to consider that the grades in major subjects, emotional quotient status, socioeconomic status and attitude towards CPA review could probably affects the performance of the students in the national professional examination such as CPA Licensure Examination. Henceforth, it is recommended to strictly implement the retention policy, devise a program concerning maintaining higher level of emotional quotient of every student, strengthen the sustainability of the JPIA's incentive program and increase awareness of the students about the notion of right attitude towards CPA review to improve the passing percentage in the national level examination such as Licensure Examination for Certified Public Accountant.

Keywords: *performance, CPA, examination, intervention, graduates*

Introduction

Human resources play a crucial role in the economic progress of most developing countries, such as the Philippines. Hence, education is seen as a major determinant in the transformation process (Ogundukon & Adeyemo, 2010). The extent to which the educational institution succeeds in delivering educational services effectively will be seen in the product they produce and how they rate in the government examination (Adedipe, 1985 as cited in Ogundokun & Adeyemo, 2010).

Cabrera (2009) articulated the significant role of accountants in building and development of nation. Thus, Presidential Decree Number 692, R.A no. 9298 of the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) Resolution No. 71 series of 2004 regulates the practice of accountancy in the Philippines. It is a framework for developing and nurturing competent, virtuous, productive, and well-rounded professional accountants whose standards of practice and service shall be excellent, qualitative, world-class, and globally competitive.

Salosagcol, Tiu, and Hermosilla (2011) have acknowledged Sec.4 Scope of Practice of R.A 9298, the passers of CPA Licensure Examination have an option to choose the areas they want to be with, the practice of Accountancy shall include but not limited to the following: Practice of Public Accountancy, Practice in Commerce and Industry, Practice in Education/Academe and Practice in the Government.

To give credit, Accountancy is the first ever among the professions here in the Philippines to be included in the World Trade Organization's (WTO) policy of liberalization of services as mentioned by Lopez (2010). This implies that Filipino accountants are free to compete and offer most quality services from other parts of the world in the global discipline of accounting practice.

With the aforesaid professional prerogative, many graduates are indeed trying to pass the Licensure Examination for Certified Public Accountant. In order to qualify as applicants for CPA examination, Ballada and Ballada (2012) quoted Sec. 14 of Philippine Accountancy Act of 2004, the requisites: that he is a Filipino citizen with good moral character, a holder of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Accountancy conferred by school, college, academy or institution duly recognized and/or accredited by Commission on Higher Education (CHED) or other authorized government offices; and has not been convicted of any criminal offense involving moral turpitude.

Accountancy is not only one of the modest, less expensive but also one of the most prestigious professions in the land today. Lopez

(2010) also stressed that the profession becomes feared of and dreaded of all, because it maintained the highest mortality rate among courses that required board examinations.

Indeed, Philippine CPA Licensure Examination is one of the few enduring and difficult professional examinations both in terms of coverage and complexity of testing one's knowledge of technical concepts and applications.

The percentage of successful examinees officially released by the Professional Regulations Commission, ranging from a low of 8% to a high of 37%, would consistently attest to it. Despite the mortality rate problem, accountancy emerged as one of the most sought after profession with the tremendous growth and development of business in the country today. From a dismal 43 registered Certified Public Accountants in 1923 to approximately 150,000 as of today (Rosada & Chen, 2009).

Many institutions offering the course Bachelor of Science in Accountancy felt the mortality rate problem, Divine Word College of San Jose (DWCSJ) is not spared from this difficulty. Action plans should be undertaken to be excluded from the list of low performing schools as regards to Licensure Examination for Certified Public Accountants.

In order to take part in achieving improved performance of its graduates in the Licensure Examination for Certified Public Accountants, the researcher felt the need of this study entitled, "Performance in CPA Licensure Examinations of DWCSJ Graduates: A Proposed Intervention".

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to find out what factors affect performance in CPA licensure examination of DWCSJ students. Specifically, it looked for the answers to the following questions.

1. What are the profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 grades in major subjects;
 - 1.2 intelligence quotient;
 - 1.3 emotional quotient; and
 - 1.4 socioeconomic status?
2. What is the attitude of the respondents towards CPA review?
3. What is the level of performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the level of performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the Attitude towards CPA review and the respondents' performance level in the CPA Licensure Examination?
6. What development program will strengthen the performance of the school in the CPA Licensure Examination?

Methodology

This section presents the methods of research that were utilized in this study. It discusses also the respondents, the research instruments, and the data gathering procedure as well as the statistical techniques that were employed to answer the research problems of the study.

Research Design

Basically, the nature of this study is descriptive research using descriptive-correlational design. The said method of research is applicable to seeking answers about the relationships of grades in major subjects, IQ level, EQ status, attitude towards CPA review, and socioeconomic status to their performance in the CPA Licensure Examination. Two null hypotheses were tested, and the confirmation or rejection of which were likewise used to answer specific questions.

Participants

The respondents of the study were classified into two (2) groups: CPA passers and non-passers. It involves sixty two (62) CPA and seventy four (74) non-passers. Data taken were based on the result of Licensure Examination for Certified Public Accountant, consolidated by the Secretary of the Vice President for Academic Affairs and certified true and correct by the Dean of College of Accountancy.

Instruments

The questionnaire is the main research instrument used for the gathering of data. It is specifically designed for the purpose and is patterned from relevant and related literature. The Respondents' Questionnaire was composed of three parts: EQ Status, Attitude towards CPA Review and Socioeconomic status. For the first part, it determined the socioeconomic status of parents in terms of monthly gross income when they took the examination. The second part determined the respondent's emotional status, as modified from the BarOn EQ-i:s Questionnaire. It classified emotional status into five (5): Self-Awareness, Self-Regulation, Self-Motivation, Empathy and Social Skills. The last part on the other hand concentrated on the attitude of respondents towards review, as adapted from Queen University: Learning Strategies Development Inventory.

To formulate the items on Part II and Part III of the questionnaire, the schema is presented as follows:

<i>Emotional Quotient</i>	–	20	items
Attitude towards CPA review	–	20	items
Total	-	40	items

In responding to the Part II of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to rate each statement by checking the box, which corresponds to their level of agreement by using the scale of:

5– Strongly Agree; 4 – Agree; 3 – Uncertain; 2 – Disagree; 1– Strongly Disagree

For the Part III of the questionnaire, the respondents were asked to rate each item by using the scale below:

5 – Always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – Rarely; 1- Never

Part of the study is the IQ Level of the respondents. This information was collected from Guidance Counselor. It is a result from the standardized test named STANINE IQ Test. The descriptions of the scores are the following: 0-3 below average, 4-6 average, and 7-9 above average.

Procedure

To identify the names and numbers of respondents, the proponent requested a list of copies from the office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs and Dean of the College of Accountancy.

Request letter to conduct the study has been noted by the adviser and approved by the Vice President for Academic Affairs. Validated questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and retrieved personally by the researcher. Considering that some of the respondents are no longer in San Jose, the researcher used also email and facebook for easy retrieval and follow up interview to solve the answered questions.

The grades in major subjects of the respondents during their undergraduate course determine their academic performance. It is the result of their effort and ability during their college life. The researcher asked permission from the Office of the Registrar to obtain a copy of grades to be used in this research study.

A part of this study is to test the relationship of IQ level with their performance in licensure examination. The researcher seeks the consent of the Guidance Counselor for the results of respondent's IQ level. The EQ status, attitude towards CPA review and socioeconomic status of the respondents were identified through the questionnaires that were sent to them. The results were tabulated, presented, analyzed and interpreted by the researcher with the guidance of his adviser and statistician.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the statistical analysis and interpretation of the gathered data that ultimately answer the inquiries sought in the study. The results were presented according to the sequence of problems questions listed in Chapter I.

Problem 1. What are the profiles of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1 grades in major subjects;
- 1.2 intelligence quotient;
- 1.3 emotional quotient; and
- 1.4 socioeconomic status?

In the Certified Public Accountant Licensure Examination, there are seven subjects needed to be passed by every examinee in order for him to be counted in rosters of CPA. These subjects are Auditing Problem (AP), Auditing Theory (AT), Business Law and Taxation (BLT), Management Advisory Services (MAS), Practical Accounting 1 (P1), Practical Accounting 2 (P2), and Theory of Accounts (TOA).

The abovementioned syllabi in CPA Licensure Examination have equivalent professional subjects during their undergraduate courses. These are Accounting 1&2, Accounting 5&6, Accounting 5&6A, Accounting 5&6B and Accounting 12&13 for the composition of Auditing Problems; the Auditing Theory is comprised of Accounting 10 and Accounting 12&13; Business Law & Taxation are the integration of Law 1 to 4 and Taxation 1 to 2; Accounting 7&8, Accounting 15, Accounting 16 and Accounting 16A were incorporated for Management Advisory Services; Accounting 1&2, Accounting 5&6, Accounting 5&6A and Accounting 5&6B for Practical Accounting 1; Accounting 3&4, Accounting 7&8, Accounting 9, Accounting 11 and Accounting 14 for Practical Accounting 2; and Theory of Accounts encompassed Accounting 1&2, Accounting 5&6, Accounting 5&6A and Accounting 5&6B.

From Table 2 to Table 8 the grades of the respondents in their major subjects were presented.

Table 1. *Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Auditing Problems*

<i>AP</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	8	5.9
80-84	46	33.8
85-89	68	50.0
90-94	14	10.3
Total	136	100.0

Table 1 shows the performance of the respondents in their major subject, Auditing Problems.

Exactly 50% or sixty eight (68) respondents attained ratings from 85-89. Forty six (46) of them correspond to 33.8% which obtained grades ranging from 80-84. The 10.3% of the population garnered grades of 90-94. Eight (8), which represents 5.9%, received ratings in between 75-79.

Prior studies revealed that college grade is a good benchmark to predict the success of examinees in licensure examination (Leana & Pil, 2006; Zvoch & Stevens, 2006; Lietz, 2009).

Table 2. *Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Auditing Theory*

<i>AT</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	10	7.4
80-84	62	45.6
85-89	50	36.8
90-94	13	9.6
95-100	1	.7
Total	136	100

Only one (1) or .7% in the entire population achieved the highest-grade range of 95-100. There were sixty-two (62) respondents who obtained average grades ranging from 80-84. This corresponds to 45.6% of the entirety. However, there are 50 respondents or 36.8% who entered the grade bracket of 85-89. While thirteen (13) have garnered ratings ranging from 90-94 which shows 9.6% of the total population. Ten (10) or 7.4% got a grade between 75-79.

Among the seven (7) major subjects, Table 3 shows that the students experienced difficulty in Auditing Theory. On the contrary, career success is not always predicted by school performance (Wundt, cited in Sternberg et al., 2012).

Table 3. *Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Business Law and Taxation*

<i>BLT</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	2	1.5
80-84	33	24.3
85-89	64	47.1
90-94	37	27.2
Total	136	100

Sixty four (64) or 47.1% of the students were able to achieve a mark between 85-89. The respondents who performed above average were 27.2% or 37 respondents. Their grades range from 90-94. Thirty three (33) or 24.3% of the respondents obtained grade of 80-84. There are two (2) or 1.5% marked grade of 75-79.

Table 3 indicates that among seven (7) subjects, the respondents performed well in Business Law and Taxation. Past researches indicated that one of the good success indicators in licensure examination is college grade (Hoffman, 2002; Garton, Dyer, & King, 2000; Munro, 1981; as cited in Diaz, 2013; Pascua, 2012; Rende, Rende, & Baysal, 2006; Zheng, Saunders, Shelley, & Whalen, 2002).

Table 4. *Respondents' Profile In Terms of Grade in Management Advisory Services*

<i>MAS</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	4	2.9
80-84	52	38.2
85-89	60	44.1
90-94	20	14.7
Total	136	100

Table 4 reveals that sixty of the total one hundred thirty-six (136) respondents performed satisfactorily in Management Advisory Services subject. This corresponds to the grade bracket of 85-89. There were fifty-two (52) or 38.2% who obtained ratings of 80-84. Twenty (20) or 14.7% achieved above average grades that ranged from 90-94. Only four or 2.9% attained grades of 75-79.

Based on the table, it can be assumed that generally, the respondents performed satisfactorily in their Management Advisory Services subject. It also substantiates that the respondents' quantified scores either high or low are indicators of performance evaluation in licensure examination (Adedipe, 1998).

Table 5. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Practical Accounting 1

<i>P1</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	7	5.2
80-84	35	25.7
85-89	77	56.6
90-94	17	12.5
Total	136	100

Table 5 shows the performance of the respondents in their major subject, Practical Accounting 1. Seventy-seven (77) out of one hundred thirty-six (136) or 56.6% obtained grades from 85-89. There were thirty-five (35) who reached the grade of 80-84. A total of seventeen (17), corresponds to 12.5% of the entire respondents achieved a grade range of 90-94. Only seven (7) or 5.1% among them garnered grades ranging from 75-79. This affirms that the respondents attain different grades even in the same subject is the most reliable individual difference index relative to achievement (Jonassen & Grabowski, 1993; as cited in Weymer, 2002).

Table 6. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Practical Accounting 2

<i>P2</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
80-84	36	26.5
85-89	75	55.1
90-94	25	18.4
Total	136	100

Table 6 shows the performance of the respondents in their major subject, Practical Accounting 2.

Majority of the respondents which comprised to 55.1% earned grades in between 85-89. There were thirty-six or 26.5% who got grades within the range of 80-84. A percentage of 18.4 represents respondents who obtained grades from 90-94.

Based on the result, the respondents' achievement in this subject is dissimilar from each other; it shows how they apply knowledge acquired differently which outcomes have seen in their performance in actual examination (Lahey, 2004).

Table 7. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Grade in Theory of Accounts

<i>TOA</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
75-79	8	5.9
80-84	39	23.7
85-89	68	50.0
90-94	21	15.4
Total	136	100

Fifty percent (50%) of one hundred thirty-six (136) respondents garnered a grade ranging from 85-89. Thirty-nine (39) or 23.7% of them got grades ranging from 80-84.

Those grades within the range of 75-79 obtained 5.9% of the totality. A grade bracket from 90-94 has 15.4% or 21 of the whole group.

Even though, the respondents are taking the same subject, their academic performance are different which according to Sonza (2008) college grade is a determining factor of success in licensure examination.

Table 8. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Intelligence Quotient

<i>Intelligence Quotient</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent Distribution</i>
Average	123	90.4
Above Average	13	9.6
Total	136	100

Table 8 exhibits the intelligence quotient of the respondents. It can be gleaned from the table that most of the respondents have an average intelligence quotient corresponding to 90.4% or one hundred twenty-three (123) out of one hundred thirty-six (136). There are thirteen (13) or 9.6% respondents whose intelligence quotient level is above average.

The data above support that the IQ level of the respondents varies. IQ is an abridged mode of conveying relative performance (Davidoff, cited in Sternberg et al., 2012).

Several literatures determined that person with a higher intelligence quotient tend to attain a higher level of performance in licensure examination (Sanchez et al., 1996; Ceci & Bankston, 1997).

Valencia (2002) also insisted the same idea that intelligence quotient is important factor in licensure examination because considering the actual questions in examination involves wide-ranging topics. Furthermore, CPA Licensure Examination implicates comprehensive queries; higher order of thinking is noteworthy (Sevilla et al., 2012).

Table 9. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Emotional Quotient

Emotional Quotient	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
I use positive emotions as sources of wisdom in navigating my life.	4.32	Very High Extent
I am calm under pressure.	3.82	High Extent
When challenged, I am good at becoming calm and focused on the flow of life's demands.	3.90	High Extent
I am in charge of what I feel.	4.13	High Extent
After something has upset me, I find it easy to regain my composure.	3.95	High Extent
I am effective in listening to other people's problems.	4.08	High Extent
I am sensitive to emotional needs of others.	4.12	High Extent
I try to be creative with life's challenges.	4.21	Very High Extent
I respond appropriately to other people's moods.	3.87	High Extent
I face my negative feelings and work through the issue.	3.93	High Extent
I am capable of soothing myself after an upsetting event.	3.98	High Extent
Knowing my true feelings is crucial to my well-being.	4.06	High Extent
I am adept at reading other people's feelings by their facial expressions.	3.90	High Extent
I can easily set aside negative feelings when called upon perform	3.93	High Extent
I am aware of subtle social signals that indicate what others need.	3.93	High Extent
I consider myself as an effective coach for other's emotions.	3.93	High Extent
I believe that people who are aware of their true feelings are better pilots of their lives.	4.38	Very High Extent
I am strongly attuned to other's feelings.	3.97	High Extent
I help others use their motivations to achieve their personal goals.	4.01	High Extent
I can easily shake off negative feelings.	3.88	High Extent
Overall Mean	4.01	High Extent

Displayed in Table 9 is the mean perception of respondents on emotional quotient. This is evidenced by a high overall mean rating of 4.01.

It could be noticed that three (3) items registered a very high extent of perception. The respondents' discernment is expressed in using positive emotions as sources of wisdom in navigating life (mean=4.32), in trying to be creative with life's challenges (mean=4.21) and believing that people who are aware of their true feelings are better pilots of their lives (mean=4.38).

The remaining items were perceived to a high extent having mean rating from 3.82 to 4.13. The fourth item recorded the highest mean of 4.13. This refers to the statement that "I am in charge of what I feel". This is closely followed by the 7th item having 4.12 as a mean for being sensitive to the emotions of others.

Items number 10, 14, 15 and 16 with the following statements "I face negative feelings and walk through the issue", "I can easily set aside negative feelings when called upon to perform", "I am aware of subtle social signals that indicate what others need" and "I consider myself as an effective coach for other's emotion", respectively, registered a mean of 3.93. And the last item I am calm under pressure, with a mean of 3.82. A great deal of research denotes that emotions may be helpful or harmful depending upon their intensity. The person with mastery and control of emotions can both anticipate and plan emotional reactions to maximize effectiveness (Lynn, 2002). Numerous research studies signify the pattern association between emotional quotient and academic performance is plethora (Ogundokun & Adeyemo, 2010).

Table 10. Respondents' Profile on Socioeconomic Status

SES	Frequency	Percent Distribution
Below P10,000	9	6.6
P10,000-P19,999	34	25
P20,000-P29,999	47	34.6
P30,000-P39,999	26	19.1
P40,000 and above	20	14.7
Total	136	100

Table 11 reveals that 34.6% or 47 of them has family gross income per month ranging from P20,000-P29,999. Earnings between P10,000-P19,999 has a frequency of 34 or 25%. Twenty six (26) or 19.1% produced P30,000-P39,999 while those who earn a revenue of P40,000 and above equates to 14.7% of the total populace. While, 6.6% or 9 out of 136 respondents belong to the bracket of below P10,000 which happened to be the least frequency.

Socioeconomic status in this study refers to the gross income of the family at the time they took the licensure examination.

As we observed from the table above, respondents' socioeconomic status differ. Many studies consistently affirm that socio-economic status influences the examinees outcome. More resources they have, greater likelihoods to succeed in the said licensure examination (Baharudin & Luster, 1998; Jeynes, 2002; Eamon, 2005; Majoribanks, 1996; Hochschild, 2001; Seyfried, 1998; as cited in Barry, 2006).

Problem 2. What is the attitude of the respondents towards CPA review?

Table 11. Respondents' Mean Perception on Attitude Towards CPA Review

Attitude towards CPA Review	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
When I decide to study, I can start and keep on going.	3.94	High Extent
To assess my performance, I take the chapter self-test.	3.99	High Extent
The ideas I hear from my co-reviewees help me learn more.	4.04	High Extent
I am able and willing to ask for help when I need it.	4.02	High Extent
I use relaxation techniques and exercises to condition myself in a positive mood for study.	3.88	High Extent
I can focus my attention without too much effort.	3.66	High Extent
I get the latest edition of the book on the subject matter under study.	3.74	High Extent
I am calm when taking an exam.	3.86	High Extent
I seek help from a reviewer in order to properly understand the topic.	3.35	Moderate
When I like the topic, I usually find out more information about it.	4.07	High Extent
It motivates me to compete with my co-reviewees to get higher scores than them.	3.73	High Extent
I am up to date with lessons from the review classes.	3.93	High Extent
I listen attentively in review class.	4.13	High Extent
I make a master schedule for each week.	3.82	High Extent
I connect ideas from one lecture to another.	3.82	High Extent
I enjoy sharing my ideas with my co-reviewees in order to retain the topics easily.	4.06	High Extent
I persevere even if the review is boring.	3.90	High Extent
I think I will get passing grades.	3.99	High Extent
I am able to study subjects that I don't really like.	3.88	High Extent
I utilize different study techniques to preserve the information	3.91	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.89	High Extent

In a five point scale of very high (4.2-5.0), high (3.4-4.19), moderate (2.6-3.39), low (1.8-2.59) and very low (1.0-1.79), the attitude of the respondents towards CPA review results to an overall mean of 3.89 which is interpreted as high extent.

Remarkably, nineteen (19) out of twenty (20) questions were recorded with a high extent description. Out of twenty items, only one reveals the moderate description having a 3.35 mean. It corresponds to 9th item; I seek help from a reviewer in order to properly understand the topic. The highest mean of 4.13 refers to the item number 13 which states that I listen attentively in review classes. The perception that they will get passing grades registered a mean of 3.99 which got the same mean on the statement of "to assess my performance, I take the chapter self-test". The respondents persevere even if the review is boring attained the mean of 3.90. With the findings above, the attitude of the respondents is highly described. This implies that the respondents have positive mental attitude which is needed by every aspirant (Valencia, 2002).

Further, it set forth that personality traits such as self-efficacy abetted students persevere when they encounter the academic and social challenges. They are tough and have better established self-concept and are more self-possessed about the ability to achieve successful effort during difficult circumstances. With that, the students improve their habits and attitudes in pursuing their goals which is understood as motivation in their undertakings (Bean & Eaton, 2000).

A lot of research verified that there is positive correlation between attitudes and performance (Copper-Hakim & Viswesvaran, 2005; Harrison, Newman, & Roth, 2006; Judge et al., 2001; Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, & Topolnysky, 2002; Riketta, 2002).

Problem 3. What is the level of performance of the examinees?

Table 12. Respondents' Performance Level

	Frequency	Percentage Distribution
Non-Passers	74	54.4
Passers	62	45.6
Total	136	100

Table 12 displays that non passers are greater than the number of passers. Majority of the respondents are non- passers with a total number of 74 or 54.4% of the total population compared with passers who garnered only 45.6% of the examinees.

CPA Licensure Examination becomes feared of all college students taking Accountancy course because it maintained highest mortality rate problem among courses that required board examinations (Lopez, 2010). The extent to which the educational institution succeeds in delivering educational services effectively will be seen in the product they produce and how they rate in the government examination (Adedipe, 1985 as cited in Ogundokun et al. 2010). Consequently, Divine Word College of San Jose is one of many colleges and universities all over the country having a difficulty in improving the passing percentage of CPA Licensure Examination.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the profiles and the level of performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination?

Table 13 reveals the results of the analysis as the respondents' profiles were regressed towards their level of performance in the CPA examination.

Four sets of variables were tested to establish the probable relationship with the examinees' performance level. The respondents' grade in seven major subjects, their level of intelligence quotient, emotional quotient and socio-economic status comprise the aforementioned independent variables. The regression computations employed the stepwise technique, and which are set at the 0.05 significance level.

Table 13. *Multiple Regression Analysis Between Respondents' Profiles and Their Level of Performance*

<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Variable That Entered the Regression Model</i>	<i>Multiple r</i>	<i>Adjusted r^2</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Performance Level	Grade in major subjects	0.547	0.294	7.201	0.00
	Emotional Quotient	0.569	0.314	2.336	0.021
	Socio-economic Status	0.586	0.329	1.998	0.048

Interestingly, results show that except intelligence quotient, the three variables, namely: accounting subjects' grade, emotional quotient and socio-economic status entered the regression model. Multiple r values of 0.547, 0.569 and 0.586 prove the moderate relationship with performance level. The relationship between these variables can be attested by the determination coefficients (adjusted r^2) of 0.294, 0.314, and 0.329, respectively. This means that about 29.4%, 31.4% and 32.9% of the respondents' variability in the CPA examination performance can be attributed to the variability in the grades they obtained in accounting subjects, their level of emotional quotient and their socio-economic status, correspondingly.

The significance of the relationship between the performance level and the independent variables is further strengthened by t test results corresponding to 7.201, 2.336 and 1.998 for grades, emotional quotient, and socio-economic status. These t values are held significant at 0.000, 0.021 and 0.048 levels. It can therefore be inferred that the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the examinees' profiles and their CPA performance level is rejected.

The regression results are indicative of the influence of the accounting students' grades in their major subjects, their emotional quotient and socio-economic status to how students perform in the CPA examination. This implies that students with high grades in their major subjects, with their high level of emotional quotient and who belong to the high socio-economic status will likely achieve better performance in the CPA examination.

However, it is quite surprising to note that in this study, the respondents' intelligence quotient did not pose an influence to their performance level in the CPA examination. Similarity of this finding is found in Goleman's (1996) argument that when it comes to predicting success in life, emotional quotient may be a better predictor than intelligence quotient.

The correlation between the grades in major subjects in accounting course and the CPA performance is found parallel to the findings that a good predictor of success in licensure examination is the college grade (Hoffman, 2002; Garton, Dyer, & King, 2000). Researchers Guthrie, Van, Hancock, Solomon, Anderson and McCann (1998) also found a moderate correlation between prior knowledge and examinees performance in examination. Similar findings are indicated in Ormrod's (2006) study that better learning serves as a tool of an examinee to have good performance in licensure examination.

The significant association between emotional intelligence and performance is supported by several researchers as cited by Ogundokun and Adeyemo (2010). In addition, Lynn (2002) recorded that the person with mastery and control of emotions can both anticipate and plan emotional reactions to maximize effectiveness.

In terms of socio-economic status, published articles showed medium to strong relationship between achievement and socio-economic level (White, 2002). This is corroborated by the research results of the American Psychological Association (2012) which disclosed that students with lower socioeconomic status tend to have lower and slower academic achievement as compared with students of higher socioeconomic status. Sirin (2005) also cited studies that showed a person in the higher socioeconomic status will have a greater chance of success because of the availability of the resources.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude towards CPA review and the level of performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination?

Table 14. *Correlational Analysis Between Respondents' Attitude Towards CPA Review and Their Level of Performance*

<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>Variable That Entered the Regression Model</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>Adjusted r^2</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Performance Level	Attitude Towards CPA Review	0.684	0.464	10.852	0.00

Another independent variable, attitude towards CPA review has been tested to establish a possible relationship with the respondents' level of performance in terms of CPA result. The variable attitude, as used in this study emphasizes the representation, motivation, traits, feelings and behavior of the examinee towards his/her formal review classes.

Table 14 discloses the correlational analysis between the dependent variable, students' CPA performance level and their attitude towards CPA review. The result reveals a high correlation coefficient of 0.684 and is backed up by the adjusted r^2 of 0.464. The determination coefficient of 46.4% suggests the high contribution of the level of examinees' attitude to the result of their performance in the CPA examination. The large t value of 10.862 is held significant at the 0.000 level. This result ascertains the rejection of the null

hypothesis of no significant relationship between the examinees’ attitude towards CPA review and their level of CPA performance.

This also suggests that the respondents’ attitude towards CPA review is a good predictor of their CPA examination performance. It can be inferred that the more positive attitude towards the CPA review an examinee manifest, the more likely he can perform well in the CPA examination.

Studies undertaken by researchers, Valencia (2002), Sevilla (2002) and some numerous findings showed similarity. It was found out that for an accounting student to become a Certified Public Accountant, he needs positive mental attitude. Moreover, positive attitude such as commitment to achieve goals and satisfaction are accompanied by better outcome of performance proved to positively correlate with the person’s performance. Their findings asserted that a person’s attitude is a major determinant of his behavior. Thus, a person who is interested in his review or studies will likely gain additional knowledge and improve his performance.

Problem 6. What development program will strengthen the performance of the school in the CPA Licensure Examination?

Development Program for Divine Word College of San Jose College of Accountancy

Key Result Area	Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Person Responsible	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Expexted Output
Faculty Development	To update faculty on contemporart concepts in different subject areas.	Attendance to the PICPA sponsored seminars	Dean of College of Accountancy Faculty	July 2014	Budget for Registration	Seminars to be re-echoed to another faculty member
		Attendance in Gov’t agencies seminars such as BIR, COA, CDA, DOF, SEC, DTL, etc.	Dean of College of Accountancy and Accountancy Faculty	October 2014	Transportation and Accommodation (Partly from the Faculty Dev’t Fund and Personal Shares)	
	To establish linkages with other Colleges & Universities in the Luzon area particularly in Region IV including benchmarking the dept’s teaching methodologies and relative aspects.	Benchmarking Trip to DWC Calapan for Reg IV-B Lipa City Colleges & Lyceum of the Philippines for Region IV-A for the NCR are visit University of the Philippines and De La Salle University.	All Accountancy Faculty	Semestral Break/before start of summer class 2014-2017	Personal contribution and part of Department Funds.	Improvement in teaching methologies & sustaining linkages with the other school’s faculty
	To encourage several faculty members earned their master’s degree	Provide scholarship and assistance to faculty with no master’s degree	Faculty with no maters’s degree		Department Office Supplies and Communication Budget	Ensure Accountancy students with recent developments and updates in all accounting areas.
	To assess the performance of faculty member specially those who holds Integrated Review Courses	Evaluation in terms of attendance, resources, teaching style and motivation on students	Dean of College of Accountancy & Vice President for Academic Affairs	Before the end of every semester	Budget the Department	Improvement in teaching methologies
Student Development	To ensure that students are provided with	Further improve the review area facilities by	College of Accountancy Offices and	School Year 2014-2015	Course Development Fund Raising	Provide students with highly improved review

	adequate Audio-Video facilities on Review Area	acquiring additional materials to be maintained in the vicinity of the College of Accountancy	Junior Philippine Institute of Accountants in coordination with the College Dean and Administrative Vice President		Projects in collaboration of College of Accountancy and JPIA officers.	area in the College which would adequately provide the proper environment as they go through the learning process.
	To encourage higher position and positive attitude of students as well as to maintain their higher level of EQ in order to perform better in the CPALE	Twice a year symposium or open forum with CPA's or authority with expertise on their respective areas.	Dean of the College of Accountancy in collaboration with PICIPA-Occidental Mindoro Chapter and CPA's who are graduates in DWCSJ	1 st Semester and 2 nd Semester of every school year	Junior Philippine Institute of Accountants and College of Accountancy Funds	Uplift the mental and emotional condition of every aspirants with regards to the purpose of being Accountancy student
	To enhance the performance of undergraduate students in their major subjects	Strict implementation of retention policy	Dean of the College of Accountancy and Accountancy Faculty Members in cooperation with JPIA officers	1 st Semester and 2 nd Semester of every School Year	Personal contributions of 1 st year and 2 nd year Accountancy Students	Students are responsible and aware to maintain their grades in major subjects
Curriculum Development	To continuously update and upgrade syllabi of the college of accountability	Review annually the syllabi of the accountancy department to CHED minimum requirement and additional subjects that deemed necessary	All faculty of the department	Summer	Budget of the Department	Perform well in qualifying examinations Ensure that syllabi of the different subject areas are upgraded
Research Development	To come up with different researchers on areas related to the Accountancy department	Conducting research on strategic management tracer study and correlation of Entrance Exam and CPA board exam	All faculty of the Department	Summer	Budget of the Department	Provide concrete database on further developing areas for student development

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are generated: (1) The respondents' profiles in terms of: (1.1) Grades in Major Subjects. The respondents performed satisfactorily in their seven (7) major subjects. It can be deduced that they acquired necessary knowledge to perform well in CPA Licensure Examination. (1.2) Intelligence Quotient. Majority of the respondents have average intelligence quotient level. This presumed that above average level of intelligence quotient is not a requisite to have a good performance in CPA Licensure Examination. (1.3) Emotional Quotient Status. The overall mean perception of the respondents on emotional quotient is verbally described as high extent. This explains that the student should make his way to enhance his status of emotional quotient to have a good performance in CPA Licensure Examination. (1.4) Socioeconomic Status. More than one-third of the respondents belong to middle family. In as far as income is concerned: this concludes that higher socioeconomic status will have greater chance of success

because of the availability to obtain the resources necessary in preparation for CPA Licensure Examination. (2) Attitude of the respondents towards CPA Review. In regard to their attitude, respondents have described high extent towards their CPA review. This would only imply that respondents are doing their part as reviewees to be ready for CPA Licensure Examination. (3) The level of performance of the examinees. More than half of the entire population is non-passers. The DWCSJ College of Accountancy must devise measure to improve the passing rate of DWCSJ CPA examinees. (4) Analysis of significant relationship between the profiles and the level performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination. The profiles in terms of grades in major subjects, emotional quotient status and socioeconomic status and the level of performance of the respondents have significant relationship. (5) Analysis of significant relationship between the attitude towards CPA review and the level of performance of the respondents in the CPA Licensure Examination. There is significant relationship between the attitude towards CPA review and the level of Performance of the respondents. (6) The development program could help the College of Accountancy students to have a good foundation; and to ensure that they are well-prepared in taking CPA Licensure Examination.

Based on the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are presented: (1) Grades in Major Subjects can predict the future performance of the students. Hence, retention policy should be strictly implemented. (2) In addition to the present guideline of at least 85% of average grades both English and Math during high school, entrance examination should also be conducted by the College of Accountancy before the incoming freshmen allowed enrolling B.S. Accountancy. (3) It will be helpful if instructors continuously improve and formulate different instructional approaches and materials to maximize the student's potential and in a way to develop their academic performance. (4) With the sample's performance, it is suggested to devise a program concerning maintaining higher level of emotional quotient of every student in order to have efficient and effective academic performance. (5) A program must be instituted by the school community towards attitude in CPA review to increase awareness of the students about the concept of syllabi in CPA Licensure Examination. (6) Since socioeconomic status affects the performance of the students, Junior Philippine Institute of Accountants (JPIA) will endure incentive program to those who got an average of 90% in major subjects and seek other benefactors to help and support the sustainability of the program. (7) To strengthen the performance of DWCSJ Accountancy students, the following action plan should be observed: continuous evaluation of in-house review program; assessment of reviewers in terms of resources, attendance and motivation on students; and increase number of full time instructor. (8) Promote classroom atmosphere conducive to learning, closely monitor students' attendance and encourage higher position of attitude on students to perform better in the CPA Licensure Examination. (9) Finally, it is recommended that more researchers be encouraged to conduct further studies and researches relative to this undertaking such as learning style of the students and teaching styles of the teachers for the upgraded Performance in CPA Licensure Examination of DWCSJ Graduates.

References

- Albarracín, D., Johnson, B. T., & Zanna, M. P. (2005). *The handbook of attitudes*. Mahwah: Erlbaum.
- Anderman, L. H., & Midgley, C. (1997). Motivation and middle school students. In J. L. Irvin (Ed.), *What current research says to the middle level practitioner* (pp. 41-48). Columbus, OH: National Middle School Association.
- Aquino, A. (2010). *Facilitating Human Learning*. Manila: Rex Book Store.
- Ballada, W., Ballada, S., (2012). *Basic Accounting*, 17th edition. Manila: Domdane Publisher
- Beck, U. (2000). *The Brave New World of Work*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bloom, B. S., & Broder, L. J. (1950). *Problem-Solving processes of Colleges Students*. Chicago: University of Chicago press
- Bornstein, M. C., & Bradley, R. H. (Eds.). (2003). *Socioeconomic status, parenting, and child development*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Brooks-Gunn, J., Denner, J., & Klebanov, P. K. (1995).
- Cabrera, E., (2009). *Assurance Principles, Professional Ethics and Good Governance*. Manila: Conanan Educational Supply
- Cabrera, E., (2011). *Comprehensive Reviewer in Auditing Theory*. Manila: GIC Enterprises & Co., Inc.
- Davidoff, L. (1993). *Introduction to Psychology*. 3rd ed. McGraw: Hill Bock Company.
- Dizon, P., Fulgencio, A. Gregorio, J., Obias, P. H., Vendivel, R., (2003). *General Psychology a Textbook for College Students*. Manila: Rex Bookstore, Co., Inc.
- Ebert II, E.S. & Culyer II, R.C. (2012). *Introduction to Education*. Singapore: Engage Learning Asia Pte.Ltd.
- Eggen, P. & Kauchak, D. (1999). *Educational Psychology: Windows on classroom*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (1993). The nature of attitudes. In A. H. Eagle & S. Chaiken (Eds.), *The psychology of attitudes* (pp. 1–21). Fort Worth: Harcourt Brace College.
- Goleman, D. (1996). *Emotional Intelligence*. New York, Bantam, Bookstore.
- Halonen, J. S., Brown-Anderson, F., & McKeachie, W. J. (2002). *Teaching thinking*. In W. J. McKeachie (Ed.), *McKeachie's*

- teachingtips: Strategies, research, and theory for college and university teachers (11th ed.). Boston: Houghton-Mifflin.
- Jonassen, D. H. & Grabowski, B. L. (1993). Handbook of individual differences: Learning and instruction. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Lahey, B. B. (2004). Psychology: an introduction. 8th ed. Boston: McGraw Hill.
- Lareau, A. (2003). Unequal Childhoods: Race, Class, and Family Life. USA: University of California Press
- Lewkowicz, A.B. (1999). Teaching emotional intelligence: Making informed choices. Arlington Heights: Skylight Training and Publishing, Inc.
- Lopez, R. (2010). Fundamentals of Accounting. Davao City: MS Lopez Printing & Publishing.
- Lynn, A. (2002). The Emotional Intelligence Activity Book: 50 Activities for Developing EQ at Work. American Management Association. New York, NY, USA
- Mayer, J.D. (2001). Emotion, Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P. & Caruso, D. (2000). Emotional intelligence meets traditional standards for an intelligence. New York: Basic Books.
- Medina R. (2011). Human Behavior in Organization. Manila: Rex Printing Company, Inc.
- Meyer, J. D., & Allen, N. J. (1997). Commitment in the workplace. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Miranda, G., and Miranda, C., (1996). Management Principles and Management. Second Revised Edition. Manila: L & G Business House
- Mison I., Bernabe L. (2004). Human Behavior in Business Organization. Manila: National Bookstore
- Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., & Steers, R. M. (1982). Employee-organization linkages: The psychology of commitment, absenteeism, and turnover. New York: Academic Press.
- Newstrom, J. W. (2007). Organizational Behavior: Human Behavior and Work (12th edition). U.S.A. McGraw-Hill International.
- Ocampo, R., (2010). Reviewer in Auditing Problems. Manila: Conan Educational Supply.
- Ormrod, J. E. 2006. Educational psychology developing learners. (5th ed.) New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Rathus, S., (2012). Cognitive Psychology, (6th edition). Philippines: ESP printers, Inc.
- Robbins, S., (2005). Organizational Behavior, (10th edition). Philippines: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Roque, G., (2012). CPA Examination Reviewer! Auditing Problems. Manila: GIC Enterprises & Co., Inc.
- Rosada, A., and Chen, H. (2009). Auditing Theory. Ilo-Ilo City: Yuency Books
- Rodriguez, D. (2012). The murder victim? Your library assumption suspects. It could have Understanding Library Impacts on Students Learning and Instruction, Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum
- Rainey, H. G. (2008). Work Motivation. Work Motivation. Encyclopedia of Public Administration and Public Policy.
- Robbin, S.P., & Judge, T.A. (2007). An Introduction to Organizational Behavior, (12th ed.). U.S.A.: Pearson Educational International.
- Sadker, David M., Sadker, M., & Zittleman, K., (2008). Teachers, Schools and Society. 8th edition Hill. New York, USA: McGraw.
- Salosagcol J., Tiu M., & Hermosilla R. (2011). Auditing Theory a guide to understanding PSA, Third Edition. Manila: GIC Enterprise and Co, Inc.
- Sanchez, C., Abad, P., & Jao, L., (1996). General Psychology, 2nd edition. Manila: Rex printing Co., Inc.
- Santrock, J. W. 2008. Educational psychology. 3rd ed. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- Sevilla, C., Punsalan, T., Rovira, L., & Vendivel, F., (2002) General Psychology with Values Development Lessons, Third Edition. Manila: Rex Bookstore, Inc.
- Sevilla, C., Punsalan, T., Rovira, L., & Vendivel, F., (2011) General Psychology with Values Development Lessons, fourth Edition. Manila: Rex Bookstore, Inc.
- Sonnentag, S. & Frese, M. (2001). Psychological Management of Individual Performance. Germany: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Sternberg R., Stenberg K. & Mio (2012) Cognitive Psychology, 6th Edition. Philippines: MG Reprographics

Sternberg, R., & Grogorenko, E. (2000). Practical Intelligence and Its Development. *The Handbook of Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Development, Assessment and Application at Home, School, and in the Workplace*. San Francisco, USA: Jossey-Bass.

Tucker, C. M., Zayco, R. A., & Herman, K. C. (2002). Teacher and Child Variables as Predictors of Academic Engagement Among Low-income African American Children. *Psychology in the Schools*, 39(4), 477-488.

Valix, C., Peralta, J. and Valix, C. A. (2013). *Financial Accounting, Vol. 3*. Manila: GIC Enterprises Co., Inc.

Valencia, E., (2002). *The Making of CPA: Secrets on How to Pass the CPA Board Examination*. Baguio: Valencia Educational Supply

Zirkel, S. (2000). Social Intelligence: The Development and Maintenance of Purposive Behavior. *The Handbook of Emotional Intelligence: Theory, Development, Assessment and Application at Home, School, and in the Workplace*. San Francisco, USA: Jossey-Bass.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mark Jing D. Tayactac, CPA, MBA, MDM
National Food Authority – Philippines